

SOCIALLY INFLUENTIAL FACTORS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIALLY ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS

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Abstract: in this article , the foreign experience of using propaganda technologies in the formation of ideological immunity , the harmony of moral qualities in the education of the youth in foreign countries, the formation of moral culture in young people, ideological propaganda, the issue of the national idea, the nation and their interdependence, the bright future of students and youth, their loyalty to their country , the effective means of developing high human qualities in determining pride are highlighted.

Key words: foreign experience, international relations, morality, culture, value, nation, social - maturity, moral virtue, high - spirituality, national pride, spirituality

On the basis of the large-scale reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is considered an urgent task to raise the young generation to be morally, spiritually and ideologically mature. In particular, Article 7 of the Law "On Education" adopted in the new version of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 23, 2020 ¹sets the task of increasing the effectiveness of the system of retraining and professional development of personnel based on modern requirements. It is determined that each of the students of higher education must have high professional potential and human qualities in the implementation of this task, and the issue of educating the future students of our country as mature personnel with professional potential and competence development by using information technology .

Pedagogical components of moral education are important in influencing the development of social activity of students. It is known that "spiritual development of the society does not happen on its own, sythically. Each system and era affects the spiritual maturity of people based on certain goals, demands and needs, gives it a meaning and a certain direction. Based on this, it is expressed ²by the origin of a system, methods and form of human education .

¹ Law "On Education". September 23, 2020 / <https://lex.uz/docs/5013007>

² Musurmonova O. Forming the spiritual culture of students. - T.: Science, 1993. - 28 p.

A. Akramov, one of the scientists of our republic, ³focused on the structural parts of the civic position of young people: he divided them into emotional-moral, intellectual, active components and explained the scientific-pedagogical basis of the process, structure, and content of the development of the civic position of students.

A. Erkaev ⁴in his scientific researches, "belief as the core of the worldview, and through it the core of spirituality, determines human attitude to reality, behavior, activity. For activity, especially for creativity, simple faith-based science is often lacking. "Creativity and activity require trust to be enriched with sincerity and love."

Robert Dahl, a professor at Yale University in the USA, one of the most famous scientists of the modern world, ⁵considers that "the danger in democracy is that many citizens do not meet the simplest standards of civil competence in practice." Because citizens are the most important factor in building civil society.

In his work, J. Rumi ⁶believes in spiritual and spiritual closeness along with physical affiliation, and he recognizes the people of meaning as the children of the saint. Because the spiritual and spiritual maturity of young people was reflected in the works of thinkers in their time.

Also, the development of socially active civic competences in students presupposes paying attention to their individual qualities. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the views of individuality pedagogy in pedagogical practice by scientists.

N. Qasimova ⁷touched on the issues of example and education in the socialization of the individual, and the fact that our enlightened grandfather Makhmudhoja Behbudi singled out the role of mutual respect between parents and children, raising children in the family, and the role of parental example in education and education also shows the place of family education in the student's social activity. it is important that it is high.

The physical, mental and spiritual maturity of the youth, mature children who have grown up on the basis of oriental manners, universal human values, democratic principles, and the successors of the work of independence is the main priority of every country that has chosen the path of independent development ⁸.

Analyzing the information presented above, the development of socially active civic competence allows a person to have an active civic position in society,

³ Akramov A. Improvement of organizational methodical bases of development of civic position of future teachers on the basis of person-oriented educational technologies. Ped.science.doc.diss..Authorref.: -T., 2016. 16 pages

⁴ Erkaev A. National idea and spirituality.: T. "Spirituality". 2002. 52-p.

⁵ Dal Robert A.. Problemy grajdanskoy kompetentnosti [Electrical resource]- URL : <http://www.politicalscience.org/library/theory/dahl.php> 15.02.2010.

⁶ Rumi J. Spiritual masnavi. Muhammad's translation. Tehran, 2001, p. 7. Persian-Uzbek dictionary .

⁷ Kasimova N.D. Importance of exemplary social psychological features in the socialization of teenagers.:diss. PIs.fn.: -T., 2010 -46 pages

⁸ Rosin V. Subject and status philosophy of education // Philosophy of education.: sb. nauchnyx statey. // ot.r. A. N. Kochergin. - M.: 1996. - S. 7-21

to ensure his active participation in the way of building a democratic state, social partnership, public control, as well as self-control, indifferent to the events and processes occurring in the life of society. not being, is manifested in the development of all the main areas of social factors of young people.

In the educational system of foreign countries, the idea of building a democratic state in increasing the activity of young people is manifested in their active participation with their thoughts and views in the activities of public organizations ⁹:

- petitioning state authorities and local self-government bodies in their activities (individual and collective appeals of citizens);
- openness of information about government activities for citizens (informational transparency of state bodies for citizens);
- participation in the management of community affairs through local self-government, citizen associations;
- public hearings;
- public discussions of bills and other important issues of state life;
- public examination of draft legislative documents;
- youth initiatives play an important role in the formation of civil society in the implementation of journalistic investigations and other types of control.

The country is on the way to "build a democratic legal state and an open civil society that ensures the observance of human rights and freedoms, the moral renewal of society, the formation of a socially oriented market economy, and integration into the world community" [2]. In any society, the factor that affects the education of the learner, i.e., the student, is an important factor to strengthen his enthusiasm, to form the skills of independent work, and to develop the initiative of a socially active person. That is why social justice plays an important role in increasing the social activity of young people in the society. It is important to emphasize that social justice means ensuring the equality of all citizens before the law, regardless of their political views, gender, nationality, language and religious beliefs. In the opinions expressed by scientists, socially active citizenship qualities of a person through the factors affecting individual qualities are important in the realization of their potential by young people. That is, there is a great possibility of influencing factors such as intellectual, motivational, emotional, volitional, self-control.

⁹ Knyazev A. Grazhdanstvennost kak slagaemoe social-political competence lichnosti . Problemy kachestva obrazovaniya. - M. - Issledovatel'skiy tsentr problem kachestva podgotovki spetsialistov. : 2003 g.

Intellectual in the field, types and style of thinking, quality of mind, cognitive processes and skills, thinking operations, as well as scientific and pre-scientific knowledge, skills and competences form a system.

The motivational field covers the set of needs, motives and goals that form and develop throughout a person's life.

Emotional the domain includes emotions, feelings, self-esteem, anxiety. Emotions[88] are related to the satisfaction or non-satisfaction of needs and are manifested in the form of immediate experiences. Positive emotions occur when meeting needs, successfully achieving the goal of activity, and help to implement them more effectively. His stable emotional relations, which reflect the importance of the phenomena of existence related to the needs and motives of a person, are called feelings. In this regard, the sense of citizenship, patriotism, sense of civic responsibility noted by many researchers is also important. It is very important to feel responsible for the fate of one's society, nation, and state, to fulfill one's civic duty and obligation.

Therefore, a person should be able to subordinate his instinctive-needs sphere to social significance in his activities, and know how to mobilize himself for future actions based on the interests of society. Protection of one's civil rights plays an important role **in voluntary self-control**, occupation and protection of socially significant situation, establishment and strengthening of civil society and democratic state. Because a person needs to feel responsible, to develop the ability to protect not only his own, but also other citizens' civil rights and interests when necessary.

Civil society envisages the freedom to choose the goals of life and the means to achieve them. It is precisely this that characterizes the field of self-management. Students and young people should be able to consciously approach the choice of their goals and aspirations based on the concepts of fairness, honesty, purity, conscientiousness, know how to think critically and comprehensively, connect their own behavior with the actions of other people, and know how to correctly evaluate their own independent thoughts and actions. It largely depends on reflexive skills, self-control, because people who look for the reasons for failures in their own behavior or qualities first, and not in external circumstances, succeed.

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